

H2020 - INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP - Leadership in enabling and industrial technologies - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

ICT-14-2016: Big Data PPP: cross-sectorial and cross-lingual data integration and experimentation

**BIG DATA
OCEAN**

BigDataOcean

“Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications”

D3.1 BigDataOcean Linked Data Vocabularies and Metadata Repository Architecture

WP3 – Cross-Sector Semantics, Analytics and Business

Workpackage: Intelligence Algorithms

Authors:	Judie Attard, Ioanna Lytra, Fabrizio Orlandi, Maria-Esther Vidal (UBONN), Nuno Amaro (NESTER), Ariadni Michalitsi-Psarrou, Dimitris Papaspyros (NTUA)
Status:	Final
Date:	29/06/2017
Version:	1.00
Classification:	Public

Disclaimer:

The BigDataOcean project is co-funded by the Horizon 2020 Programme of the European Union. This document reflects only authors' views. The EC is not liable for any use that may be done of the information contained therein

BigDataOcean Project Profile

Grant Agreement No.: 732310

Acronym:	BigDataOcean
Title:	Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications
URL:	http://www.bigdataocean.eu/site/
Start Date:	01/01/2017
Duration:	30 months

Partners

	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Decision Support Systems Laboratory, DSSLab <u>Co-ordinator</u>	Greece
	Exmile Solutions Limited (EXMILE)	United Kingdom
	Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn (UBONN)	Germany
	Centro de Investigação em Energia REN – State Grid, S.A. – R&D Nester (NESTER)	Portugal
	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)	Greece
	Ubitech Limited (UBITECH)	Cyprus
	Foinikas Shipping Company (FOINIKAS)	Greece
	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella (ISMB)	Italy
	Instituto de Desenvolvimento de Novas Tecnologias (UNINOVA)	Portugal
	Anonymi Naftiliaki Etaireia Kritis (ANEK)	Greece

Document History

Version	Date	Author (Partner)	Remarks
0.10	29/05/2017	Judie Attard, Ioanna Lytra, Fabrizio Orlandi, Maria-Esther Vidal (UBONN)	Initial document structure
0.20	07/06/2017	Ariadni Michalitsi-Psarrou, Dimitris Papaspyros (NTUA)	Contribution to the document structure
0.30	08/06/2017	Judie Attard, Ioanna Lytra, Fabrizio Orlandi, Maria-Esther Vidal (UBONN)	Draft of Chapter 2 and Chapter 6.1
0.31	09/06/2017	Nuno Amaro (NESTER)	Contributions to Chapter 2
0.40	16/06/2017	Judie Attard, Ioanna Lytra, Fabrizio Orlandi, Maria-Esther Vidal (UBONN)	Preparation of version for internal review
0.41	22/06/2017	Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis (EXMILE), Joao Pina (UNINOVA), Dimitris Papaspyros (NTUA)	Final Review
1.00	22/06/2017	Fabrizio Orlandi, Ioanna Lytra (UBONN)	Address review comments and preparation of final version

Executive Summary

This deliverable documents the results of Task 3.1 and Task 3.2, which are focused on developing the necessary infrastructure for accessing and sharing Linked Big Data vocabularies and metadata, and also deploying the related BigDataOcean services that allow for the collection, harmonisation, and processing of multi-source big maritime data. This deliverable provides an initial version of the linked data vocabularies that will be used within the project. In this aspect, it discusses the requirements for the Linked Big Data Vocabularies and the Metadata Repository that are developed in the context of BigDataOcean. In addition, this deliverable also details the architectural design of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository. Here, the different components, as well as the data model of the Metadata Repository are presented, along with the relevant use cases. With the aim of analysing existing related work, an overview of existing metadata repositories in the maritime domain is provided, and the comparison with the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository is discussed. Thereafter, this deliverable demonstrates the implemented metadata repository, as well as the existing ontologies and vocabularies that will be used within it.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	8
1.1	Objective of the Deliverable	8
1.2	Structure of the Deliverable	8
1.3	Positioning within the project	8
2	Vocabulary and Metadata Repository Requirements in BigDataOcean.....	10
2.1	Vocabulary Requirements in BigDataOcean	10
2.2	Metadata Requirements in BigDataOcean Metadata Repository	15
2.3	Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of BigDataOcean Metadata Repository.....	16
3	Architectural Design of BigDataOcean Metadata Repository	19
3.1	BigDataOcean Metadata Repository Architecture	19
3.2	Entity-Relationship Model	20
3.3	Use Cases	21
3.4	BigDataOcean Metadata Repository API	23
4	Existing Metadata Repositories in the Maritime Domain	24
5	BigDataOcean Metadata Repository Implementation	26
6	BigDataOcean Vocabularies	30
7	Conclusions	33

List of Figures

Figure 1: BigDataOcean Metadata Repository high-Level architecture.....	19
Figure 2: Entity-Relationship diagram representing the entities and properties to be captured in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository along with their relations	21
Figure 3: BigDataOcean Metadata Repository Use Case Diagram	22
Figure 4: Visualisation of vocabularies in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository.....	27
Figure 5: Presentation of vocabulary metadata	28
Figure 6: Editing of vocabulary metadata.....	28
Figure 7: SPARQL endpoint for querying vocabularies and their metadata	29
Figure 8: Visualisation of vocabularies in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository and their interconnections	29

List of Tables

Table 1: List of datasets to be used as input / output in the four BigDataOcean pilots.....	10
Table 2: Dataset descriptions for selected representative datasets	12
Table 3: Metadata requirements for the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository	15
Table 4: Primary requirements of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository	16
Table 5: Secondary requirements of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository	17
Table 6: BigDataOcean Metadata Repository basic API	23
Table 7: List of Ontologies and Vocabularies in BigDataOcean	30
Table 8: List of Ontologies and Vocabularies for datasets and dataset quality in BigDataOcean	32

List of Abbreviations

AIS – Automatic Identification System
 API – Application Programming Interface
 ATON – Aid to Navigation
 CRUD – Create, Read, Update and Delete
 CSV – Comma-separated values
 Dx.y – Deliverable x.y
 ECMWF – European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
 IMO – International Maritime Organization
 ISO – International Organization for Standardization
 LOV – Linked Open Vocabularies
 MMSI – Maritime Mobile Service Identity

Mx – Month x
NOAA – National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NSF – National Sanitation Foundation
OGC – Open Geospatial Consortium
ONR – Office of Naval Research
REST – Representational state transfer
SKOS – Simple Knowledge Organization System
SOAP – Simple Object Access Protocol
Tx.y – Task x.y
UML – Unified Modeling Language
URI – Uniform Resource Identifier
W3C – World Wide Web Consortium

1 Introduction

1.1 Objective of the Deliverable

This deliverable is based on Task 3.1 and Task 3.2, which are focused on developing the necessary infrastructure for accessing and sharing Linked Big Data vocabularies and metadata, and also deploying the related BigDataOcean services that allow for the collection, harmonisation, and processing of multi-source maritime big data. This deliverable therefore has the aim of providing a first version of the linked data vocabularies that will be used within the project. It will hence document the various requirements of vocabularies and metadata to be used in BigDataOcean, focusing on both functional and non-functional requirements. Documentation is also provided on the metadata and properties that need to be persisted in the metadata repository.

Apart from the documentation of the vocabularies and metadata that will be used in BigDataOcean, this deliverable also provides a report on the metadata repository architecture. After providing a discussion comparing existing metadata repositories in the maritime domain, this deliverable provides details on the BigDataOcean metadata repository implementation, which also includes an initial list of Linked Data Vocabularies that will be imported in the repository.

1.2 Structure of the Deliverable

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** provides an overall introduction to this report together with the positioning of this work within the project;
- **Chapter 2** describes the vocabulary and metadata repository requirements within the project;
- **Chapter 3** documents the architecture of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository;
- **Chapter 4** provides an overview of existing metadata repositories in the maritime domain;
- **Chapter 5** documents the implementation details of the BigDataOcean metadata repository;
- **Chapter 6** provides an initial list of BigDataOcean Linked Data vocabularies that will be imported in the repository;
- **Chapter 7** concludes this deliverable by providing an overview and discussion of the results obtained in this deliverable and the future steps.

1.3 Positioning within the project

The work reported in this deliverable is based on Tasks 3.1 and 3.2. Task 3.1 involves the development of the required infrastructure for accessing and sharing Linked Big Data vocabularies and metadata amongst cross-sectorial and multi-lingual data marts. On the other hand, Task 3.2 is focused on defining and deploying the BigDataOcean services that will provide the means for collecting, harmonising, and processing multi-source maritime big data. The work described in this deliverable is also interrelated to other work packages. For instance, Deliverable D2.2 provides data source definitions on several data sources. These definitions were analysed to identify potential Linked Data vocabularies that can be

mapped to these data sources. Requirements for the entire project platform, and therefore also the Metadata Repository, have been collected in D2.2.

In the future of the project, between Month 15 and Month 19 (second phase of T3.1), new features of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository will be delivered and new vocabularies will be contributed, based on the feedback by the end users of the project. The collected vocabularies will provide a basis for D3.2, especially the harmonisation of data in BigDataOcean. Finally, the final version of the vocabularies and metadata repository will be provided at Month 19 in D3.3 - BigDataOcean Cross-Sector Semantics, Analytics and Business Intelligence Algorithms.

2 Vocabulary and Metadata Repository Requirements in BigDataOcean

This chapter discusses the requirements for the Linked Big Data Vocabularies and Metadata Repository that is developed in the context of BigDataOcean.

2.1 Vocabulary Requirements in BigDataOcean

In order to gather the vocabulary requirements that describe the datasets to be used in the BigDataOcean pilots, detailed information about the available data sources in the four pilots of BigDataOcean was captured during the requirements elicitation phase. In particular, the pilot partners provided inputs with regard to the data sources at two levels of abstraction:

- By reporting on the own data and external data to be used by each type of stakeholder involved in each of the pilots;
- By filling in the data source definition form (see Deliverable D2.1 for the Data Source Definition Form) for selected data sources.

The data source definitions were afterwards analysed to identify potential Linked Data vocabularies that can be mapped to these data sources. Table 1 reports on the datasets that will be used in the corresponding pilots where either data is owned by the partners or it is available as external data sources.

Table 1: List of datasets to be used as input / output in the four BigDataOcean pilots

Pilot 1 - Datasets	
Own	External
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical data on incidents, casualties, results of inspections • Feedback received from vessels' crews and domain experts • Weather data • Vessels' routes and related incidents • Equipment installations and maintenance plans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buoys measurements indicating ripple levels, water speed, water temperature, etc.
Pilot 2 - Datasets	
Own	External
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poseidon in-situ product and forecast data • Oil spill dispersion forecast data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vessel position and routing • Weather data • Port information • Oil spill dispersion forecast data • Fisheries data • Copernicus data

Pilot 3 - Datasets	
Own	External
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural port statistics • AIS (Automatic Identification System) terrestrial network • ATON (Aid to Navigation) installations • Observing facilities (research vessel, HF radar, glider, fixed stations, beach monitoring, satellite) • Numerical models (e.g. high-resolution ocean circulation predictions, wave forecasts, extreme sea level oscillations predictions) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numerical models (e.g. metOcean parameters) • Vessel monitoring • Logistics data • Commercial data • Administrative data • Vessel position and routing • Weather data • Port information • Shipping information pipeline (vessel position) • Vessel information and tracking data (AIS data providers)
Pilot 4 - Datasets	
Own	External
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bathymetric data • Tide forecast • Tide observations • Monitoring networks • Oceanographic forecasting data 	Datasets from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration) data • ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts) • Portuguese Hydrographical Institute • Fugro Oceanor AS • BMT ARGOS • University of Colombo (USA) • Offshore Renewables Service Provider • Pilot zone concessionaire own studies • Copernicus data

In addition, the more detailed data source definitions for some of the datasets listed above provided more insights into the entities and properties that have to be described using ontologies and vocabularies from the maritime domain. Table 2 summarises these data sources that are indicative of the datasets that will be used in the context of the BigDataOcean use cases.

Table 2: Dataset descriptions for selected representative datasets

1. Copernicus Marine Environment monitoring service (COPERNICUS - CMEMS)	
Description	Various datasets covering maritime safety, coastal and marine environment, marine resources, and weather, seasonal, forecasting and climate activities.
Link	http://marine.copernicus.eu/
Pilots	Pilot 1, Pilot 2, Pilot 4
Data format	netCDF
Language	English
Ontologies / Vocabularies used	<p>Concepts from OceanSITES (http://www.oceansites.org/docs/oceansites_user_manual_ver1_1.pdf) Parameters in In Situ TAC parameters list version 3.0.0 (http://doi.org/10.13155/40846)</p> <p>http://oceanobs.mongoos.eu/page_parameters.php</p> <p>CF conventions: http://cfconventions.org/cf-conventions/v1.6.0/cf-conventions.html</p>
Standards used	Copernicus system requirements and main list of parameters distributes (http://doi.org/10.13155/40846)
2. POSEIDON System Forecasting product- Weather, sea-state, sailing, sea-level and ocean forecasts	
Description	Monitoring, forecasting and information system for the Greek seas.
Link	http://poseidon.hcmr.gr/index.php
Pilots	Pilot 2, could be used in Pilot 1 and Pilot 3
Data format	netCDF
Language	English
Ontologies / Vocabularies used	<p>CF conventions: http://cfconventions.org/cf-conventions/v1.6.0/cf-conventions.html</p>
Standards used	-

Table 2 (cont.): Dataset descriptions for selected representative datasets

3. POSEIDON System In-situ platforms- Oceanographic, atmospheric, biochemical time-series (POSEIDON buoy platforms - time-series)	
Description	The POSEIDON System contains a network of oceanographic buoys designed to monitor particular oceanographic phenomena in Greek waters. This collection contains five multi-parametric oceanographic mooring, three of them in deep water, which provide time-series observations of atmospheric parameters (Air-pressure, Air-temperature, measurements of wind), currents, waves, sea-water oxygen, temperature and salinity. The mooring stations are deployed, operated and maintained by HCMR. The observations were made using a range of temperature loggers, conductivity-temperature-depth (CTD) instruments, and temperature sensors on acoustic Doppler current profilers (ADCPs).
Link	http://env1.hcmr.gr/db_poseidon/
Pilots	Pilot 2, could be used in Pilot 1 and Pilot 3
Data format	NetCDF, json, csv
Language	English
Ontologies / Vocabularies used	Concepts from OceanSITES (http://www.oceansites.org/docs/oceansites_user_manual_ver1_1.pdf) Parameters in In Situ TAC parameters list version 3.0.0 (http://doi.org/10.13155/40846) http://oceanobs.mongoos.eu/page_parameters.php CF conventions: http://cfconventions.org/cf-conventions/v1.6.0/cf-conventions.html
Standards used	Copernicus system requirements and main list of parameters distributes (http://doi.org/10.13155/40846)
4. Portuguese Coast WaveWatch3 model data output (Nester WW3)	
Description	This dataset includes the outputs of a numerical model for forecast of waves in the Portuguese Atlantic Coast. Information contains the mean wave direction, mean wave period and significant wave height calculated for periods of 1 hour.
Link	http://forecast.maretec.org/stations/
Pilots	Pilot 4
Data format	netCDF
Language	English
Ontologies / Vocabularies used	The dataset use the CF-1.0 vocabulary
Standards used	Character set used is UTF-8 (8-bit variable size UCS Transfer Format, based on ISO/IEC 10646)

Table 2 (cont.): Dataset descriptions for selected representative datasets

5. Vessel Tracking Data collected from the Automatic Identification System (AIS)	
Description	The dataset includes the positional data of vessels that have been received by the MarineTraffic (Exmile) private AIS receivers network during 2010. This data collection contains dynamic information such as time-series observations of latitude, longitude, course over ground, speed over ground as well as a set of static information such as vessel's identification information (e.g. IMO, MMSI, etc.) that are periodically transmitted from vessels.
Link	https://www.marinetraffic.com
Pilots	Pilot 3, could be used in Pilot 2 and Pilot 4
Data format	csv
Language	English
Ontologies / Vocabularies used	The data are relying on the semantics/vocabulary as defined in ITU M1371-4 specification
Standards used	Character set used is UTF-8 (8-bit variable size UCS Transfer Format, based on ISO/IEC 10646)
6. World Port Index (Pub 150)	
Description	The World Port Index (Pub 150) contains the location and physical characteristics of, and the facilities and services offered by major ports and terminals world-wide (approximately 3700 entries), in a tabular format. Entries are organised geographically, in accordance with the diagrams located in the front of the publication.
Link	https://www.nga.mil/Pages/Default.aspx
Pilots	Pilot 3, could be used in Pilot 1, Pilot 2, and Pilot 4
Data format	MSAccess DB, Shape file
Language	English
Ontologies / Vocabularies used	-
Standards used	-

Taking into consideration the data source descriptions and the data input/output requirements discussed in this chapter, the ontologies/vocabularies that will be used to describe such datasets will need to cover the following entities:

- Vessels (positions, routing, incidents);
- Port information;

- Weather data (atmospheric);
- Sea data (bathymetric data, tide observations, water speed, water temperature, etc.);
- Waves;
- Vessel equipment;
- Vessel maintenance plans;
- Fisheries;
- Observing facilities and equipment (research vessel, radar, glider, etc.);
- Sensors (buoys, vessels, coastal stations, etc.);
- Observations and measurements;
- Measurement units.

Additional entities must be considered for describing *data sources* in the BigDataOcean platform and *vocabularies* in the Metadata Repository.

Based on these observations, an initial list of open ontologies and vocabularies has been identified. This list was afterwards validated and extended by the pilot partners during the review phase of this deliverable. Chapter 6.1 includes detailed information about the selected ontologies and vocabularies to be included in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository.

2.2 Metadata Requirements in BigDataOcean Metadata Repository

This section discusses the metadata of the ontologies and vocabularies that will be saved in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository to allow search and query capabilities, as well as interlinking. For each ontology and vocabulary in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository the following properties must be persisted in the repository.

Table 3: Metadata requirements for the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository

name	Name of the ontology / vocabulary
title	Title of the ontology / vocabulary
description	Descriptive text about the ontology / vocabulary
author	The original creator of the ontology / vocabulary
publisher	The publisher of the ontology/vocabulary
created	The date the ontology / vocabulary was created
modified	The date the ontology / vocabulary was last modified
license	The usage license of the ontology / vocabulary
rights	The usage rights of the ontology / vocabulary
format	The format of the ontology / vocabulary
language	The language of the ontology / vocabulary
numberOfProperties	Number of properties in the ontology / vocabulary

numberOfClasses	Number of classes in the ontology / vocabulary
relatedVocabulary	A vocabulary that is related to the ontology / vocabulary
homepage	Homepage URI of the ontology / vocabulary
keyword	Related keywords
usedByDataset	A Dataset that reuses the described ontology / vocabulary
usedByVocabulary	A Vocabulary that reuses the described ontology / vocabulary
comment	Any other comment describing the ontology / vocabulary
overallQualityRating	A rating that describes the overall quality of the ontology / vocabulary based on a set of given metrics
qualityMetadata	Metadata describing in higher detail level the quality of the described ontology / vocabulary
version	Version of the ontology / vocabulary
review	Reviewer and review date of the ontology / vocabulary

2.3 Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of BigDataOcean Metadata Repository

The goal of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository is to allow users importing, managing, querying and interlinking vocabularies related to the maritime domain. This section includes requirements to be met to achieve this goal. Requirements are defined based on the description of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository as well as from existing metadata repositories in the maritime domain. Two kinds of requirements are presented: *functional* and *non-functional* requirements. The functional requirements reflect the functionality of the application that will be developed while the non-functional requirements represent conditions and criteria used to evaluate the metadata repository behaviour. Furthermore, requirements are classified as primary (Table 4) and secondary (Table 5), i.e., “*must have*” and “*nice to have*” features, respectively.

Table 4: Primary requirements of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository

Primary Requirements	
Raw Requirement	Categorisation
MR-P01: Insert new vocabularies / ontologies in the Metadata Repository	Functional
MR-P02: Import existing vocabularies / ontologies into the Metadata Repository	Functional
MR-P03: Delete vocabularies / ontologies from the Metadata Repository	Functional
MR-P04: Update vocabularies / ontologies in the Metadata Repository	Functional

MR-P05: Insert metadata about vocabularies / ontologies in the Metadata Repository	Functional
MR-P06: Describe vocabularies / ontologies in the Metadata Repository using ontologies	Functional
MR-P07: Search vocabularies / ontologies in the Metadata Repository based on different criteria and keywords	Functional
MR-P08: Evaluate SPARQL queries over the Metadata Repository to collect metadata about vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-P09: Evaluate SPARQL queries over the Metadata Repository to retrieve classes and properties of vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-P10: Search and identify maritime datasets semantically enriched with particular vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-P11: Search and identify vocabularies / ontologies from similar projects in the maritime domain	Non-Functional
MR-P12: Ensure persistence of the Metadata Repository	Non-Functional
MR-P13: Ensure web-based access and availability of the Metadata Repository	Non-Functional
MR-P14: Compute statistics about the Repository vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-P15: Search pilots using particular vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-P16: Download data dumps of the Repository vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-P17: Provide a recommendation system on top of the Metadata Repository	Functional
MR-P18: Search for related vocabularies / ontologies in the Metadata Repository	Functional

Table 5: Secondary requirements of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository

Secondary Requirements	
Raw Requirement	Categorisation
MR-S01: Propagate changes in the Repository vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-S02: Link Repository vocabularies / ontologies with similar existing vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-S03: Visualise statistics about Repository vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-S04: Visualise connectivity among Repository vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-S05: Keep track of changes and versions of Repository vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-S06: Provide a Question Answering system on top of the Metadata Repository	Functional

MR-S07: Keep track of changes on the data sources described using the Repository vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-S08: Provide a SPARQL endpoint to access metadata and the Repository vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-S09: Provide Quality metric values of the Repository vocabularies / ontologies	Functional
MR-S10: Provide a Notification system to alert the Repository users whenever vocabularies / ontologies are included or updated	Functional
MR-S11: Provide an ontology validation pipeline to ensure that the Repository vocabularies / ontologies meet best practices and quality requirements	Functional

3 Architectural Design of BigDataOcean Metadata Repository

In this chapter, the details of the architectural design of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository are presented. In particular, the different components as well as the data model of the Metadata Repository are discussed and illustrated using corresponding diagrams. In addition, use cases with respect to the different Metadata Repository users are described using a UML Use Case diagram.

3.1 BigDataOcean Metadata Repository Architecture

Figure 1 contains the main components included in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository. In particular:

- **Vocabulary Importer:** This component is responsible for importing ontologies and vocabularies of different formats;
- **Metadata Management:** Is responsible for CRUD (Create, Read, Update and Delete) operations regarding all metadata; it also manages the versioning of the vocabularies;
- **Statistics:** It calculates and persists statistics about the vocabulary metadata persisted in the metadata repository;
- **Quality Metrics:** It calculates and persists quality metrics about the vocabulary metadata persisted in the metadata repository;
- **Search / Query Engine:** Provides search and query capabilities on top of the metadata persisted in the metadata repository;
- **UI:** Graphical User Interface for interaction of vocabulary publishers and consumers with the metadata repository.

On the bottom level, the vocabulary metadata refers to vocabularies that are published as Linked Open data. The BigDataOcean Metadata Repository provides a SPARQL endpoint and API that can be used by other BigDataOcean tools providing Semantic Enrichment, Data Linking, and Data Management.

Figure 1: BigDataOcean Metadata Repository high-Level architecture

3.2 Entity-Relationship Model

Figure 2 illustrates the data model used to represent the entities and their properties that are managed in the metadata repository along with the entity relationships. This is based on the observations made in Chapter 2.2. In particular, the following entities are used to describe ontologies and vocabularies in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository:

- *vocabulary*: information about a vocabulary including title, description, keywords, language, etc.;
- *version*: version of a vocabulary – a vocabulary may have one or more versions;
- *author*: creator of a vocabulary;
- *publisher*: publisher of a vocabulary;
- *curator*: curator of a vocabulary;
- *review*: a curator provides reviews for a specific version of the vocabulary;
- *right*: a vocabulary is associated with a license;
- *property*: metadata about vocabulary properties;
- *class*: metadata about vocabulary classes;
- *quality metric*: metadata describing the quality of the vocabulary according to metrics;
- *dataset*: dataset related to a vocabulary - it can be related to one or more vocabularies;
- *BDO pilot*: BigDataOcean pilot - the pilot can be related to one or more vocabularies.

For expressing the properties of the aforementioned entities various vocabularies have been referenced, such as *rdfs* (<http://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/>), *foaf* (<http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>), *vann* (vocabulary for annotating vocabulary descriptions - <http://purl.org/vocab/vann/>), and *dcterms* (Dublin Core terms - <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>).

Figure 2: Entity-Relationship diagram representing the entities and properties to be captured in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository along with their relations

3.3 Use Cases

The following Use Case diagram presents the various use cases of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository. The use cases are extracted from the Metadata Repository requirements captured in subsection 2.3. Three types of users of the system have been identified:

- **Vocabulary Creator/Publisher**: adds and manages vocabularies and vocabulary metadata in the Metadata Repository;
- **Vocabulary User**: is interested in searching the Metadata Repository for specific vocabularies, querying these vocabularies and their metadata, viewing vocabulary statistics and quality metrics, and downloading data dumps;
- **Administrator**: manages users of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository.

The use cases are related to one of the aforementioned roles, the Metadata Repository user though can play more than one of these roles.

Figure 3: BigDataOcean Metadata Repository Use Case Diagram

3.4 BigDataOcean Metadata Repository API

The BigDataOcean Metadata Repository will be accessible via a SPARQL endpoint where queries can be posed following the SPARQL protocol. Main characteristics of the vocabularies, e.g. classes, properties, and hierarchies, as well as relationships among ontologies, will be collected as the results of evaluating queries over SPARQL endpoints.

In addition, the API functions illustrated in Table 6 are already available in [LOV¹](#) and can be reused and/or extended in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository. A few of the API methods listed below related to “Agents” and users might not be fully accessible by every user as they can provide personal information. In this case they will be accessible only by the administrators of the system.

Table 6: BigDataOcean Metadata Repository basic API

Resource: Vocabulary Term (Class, Property, Datatype, Instance)	
GET	/api/v2/term/search (search for a vocabulary term)
GET	/api/v2/term/autocomplete (get autocompletion recommendations for terms)
GET	/api/v2/term/suggest (suggest a vocabulary based on terms in the repository)
Vocabulary	
GET	/api/v2/vocabulary/list (list all stored vocabularies)
GET	/api/v2/vocabulary/search (search vocabularies based on title or prefix)
GET	/api/v2/vocabulary/autocomplete (get autocompletion recommendations for vocabularies)
GET	/api/v2/vocabulary/info (get details about one vocabulary)
Agent	
GET	/api/v2/agent/list (list all users)
GET	/api/v2/agent/search (search for a user)
GET	/api/v2/agent/autocomplete (get autocompletion recommendations for users)
GET	/api/v2/agent/info (get details about one user)

¹ The BigDataOcean Metadata Repository implementation is based on LOV.

4 Existing Metadata Repositories in the Maritime Domain

Existing repositories of vocabularies in the maritime domain are described in this chapter, in terms of their main features, and the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository is positioned with respect to these approaches. The following metadata repositories are well known in the maritime domain:

(1) Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) Vocabulary Server.

NERC is a repository of vocabularies in the maritime domain². Vocabularies are described based on collections, concepts and schemas. Collections correspond to a group of related concepts, e.g. the International Coastal Atlas Network Coastal Erosion Global Thesaurus; they are annotated with publication and version related information. Concepts refer to conceptual entities that can be modelled as a Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) concept. Finally, schemes are composed of one or more concepts and relations between them. Vocabularies can be accessed using different Web services, e.g. ReSTful, SOAP API, or SPARQL endpoints. Furthermore, vocabularies are published in HTML documents of the NERC server. Although NERC allows for collecting information about its vocabularies, it does not implement a metadata repository where metadata about these vocabularies can be searched, managed, and analysed.

(2) Marine Metadata Interoperability (MMI) Repository³.

The MMI Ontology Registry and Repository has been developed in 2009 by the Marine Metadata Interoperability Project with the main goal of providing the marine community with supporting functions for semantic interoperability. The main components of the MMI repository allow users and software agents to find ontology concepts and associated annotations using semantic web based query mechanisms. There are two types of users: (i) Data Providers, who create vocabularies, term mappings, and ontologies, and register them in the repository; and (ii) Consumers, who interact with the repository to issue queries, retrieve terms, relationships, and categorisations. The MMI semantic portal offers tools that *“facilitate the creation of vocabulary and mapping ontologies. Besides being fully integrated with the portal itself, these tools provide a user interface that is simpler and less demanding, in terms of ontology expertise, than existing ontology-related software tools”*.

The MMI Repository is composed of the following main components:

- The MMI Portal, which provides the main user interface of the registry and repository.
- Voc2RDF, a tool that allows the creation of controlled vocabularies using a tabular based interface, or by importing CSV files.
- VINE, an interface for easily navigating the existing entries in the repository and establish the desired associations / mappings between terms across vocabularies. Relationships can be expressed using the SKOS vocabulary.
- A SPARQL endpoint.
- A Reasoner, which allows the repository to make automatic inferences according to encoded rules in the underlying ontological model.

² Adam Leadbitter. [NERC Vocabulary Server](#). Version 2.0. 2012.

³ <https://marinemetadata.org/>

(3) Rolling Deck to Repository (R2R)⁴.

The Rolling Deck to Repository (R2R) is supported by research agencies in the United States of America: NSF, NOAA, ONR, and SOI. R2R maintains historical and real-time sensor data observed from a collection of vessels; observed data includes meteorological, navigation, and sea surface and floor measurements. R2R provides cruise metadata consisting of expedition summaries, dataset descriptions, and models of each instrument system. Additionally, quality-controlled and post-processed data profiles are made available in the catalogue, as well as tools for at-sea even logging. The R2R catalogue ensures that entities in it are uniquely identified, and their information is persistent and accessible via lightweight and standard interfaces. Moreover, the R2R catalogue is published in multiple formats using standard vocabularies: (i) ISO 19115-2 XML metadata records, (ii) OGC Web Services, and (iii) W3C Linked Data and SPARQL endpoints; furthermore, visualisations of the catalogue resources are offered. R2R vocabularies are mapped to other standard maritime vocabularies like the NERC vocabularies; information about R2R vocabularies can be accessed from R2R SPARQL endpoints.

NERC, MMI, and R2R collections of vocabularies cover many aspects of the maritime domain; moreover, the corresponding repositories of vocabularies are available in different formats, e.g. Web services or SPARQL endpoints. Nevertheless, none of these repositories satisfy all the metadata repository requirements listed in Chapter 2.3. For example, even if attributes that describe NERC and MMI vocabularies can be accessed, datasets and projects in which vocabularies have been utilised (requirements **MR-P10** and **MR-P11**) or statistics or associations between NERC and MMI vocabularies (requirements **MR-P14** and **MR-P18**) are not available. Although diverse properties of the R2R datasets can be visualised, visualisations about specific properties of the vocabularies or connectivity across vocabularies are currently not offered by the existing systems.

⁴ <http://www.rvdata.us/>

5 BigDataOcean Metadata Repository Implementation

The BigDataOcean Metadata Repository is built on top of the Linked Open Vocabularies ([LOV](http://lov.okfn.org/)⁵) infrastructure. LOV is a generic vocabulary / ontology metadata repository that allows for registering, describing, and searching vocabularies. Currently, LOV makes available the description of more than 600 vocabularies used to describe data in the Linked Open Data cloud. Moreover, LOV relies on a publication pipeline where ontologies are reviewed by curators which decide if an ontology satisfies or not the best design practices. Additionally, instances of LOV can be created and tailored for different requirements.

The BigDataOcean metadata repository exploits the main features of LOV. However, extensions have been conducted to the LOV repository to enable the satisfaction of the BigDataOcean requirements listed in Subchapter 2.3. First, vocabularies will be described in terms of main properties, e.g. classes, predicates, hierarchies or creator, but they will be also associated with the BigDataOcean pilots in which vocabularies have been utilised. Thus, based on the relationships between the pilots and a new ontology being used in a given pilot, the BigDataOcean metadata repository will be able to recommend this ontology to the partners of the related pilots. Second, the connectivity between ontologies is defined not only based on links but also according to the associations between the datasets and pilots where these ontologies are utilised. Third, the BigDataOcean metadata repository implements a notification system that keeps tracks of the changes of the ontologies and automatically propagates these changes to the related ontologies. In this chapter, basic features of the BigDataOcean metadata repository are demonstrated. However, the first version of the repository will include the corresponding components to satisfy at least the primary requirements listed in Subchapter 2.3.

The demonstration of the main features of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository includes: (i) the visualisation of the vocabularies registered in the repository (Figure 4); (ii) the visualisation of the metadata that describes one registered ontology (Figure 5); (iii) the registration and metadata editing of one ontology (Figure 6); (iv) a SPARQL endpoint to collect both metadata about vocabularies, as well as the properties and classes that compose the ontology (Figure 7); and (v) the visualisation of links between ontologies (Figure 8).

Figure 4 depicts the ontologies included in the repository using circles, e.g. gn, ssn, and qudt. The radius of each circle denotes the number of datasets that have used the corresponding ontology, i.e., larger circles represent ontologies utilised by a large number of datasets; furthermore, ontologies with circles of similar radius are used by similar number of datasets, i.e., the same number of datasets use gn, ssn, and qudt in the current state of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository.

⁵ <http://lov.okfn.org/>

The screenshot displays the BigDataOcean Repository interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the logo 'BIG DATA OCEAN' and links for 'VOCABS', 'TERMS', 'AGENTS', and 'SPARQLDUMP'. A 'Login' link is also present. Below the navigation bar is a large blue banner with the text 'BigDataOcean Repository'. Underneath the banner, there are buttons for '+ Suggest', a Facebook icon with 'BigDataOcean', and a search input field. The main content area features a section titled '6 Vocabularies' with a visualization of three overlapping circles labeled 'gn', 'ssn', and 'qudt'. Below this visualization are 'Category Tags' for 'Vocabularies', 'W3C Rec', and 'RDF'. To the right of the visualization, there are two sections: 'Latest insertion' and 'Latest Updates'. The 'Latest insertion' section lists: 'rdfs - The RDF Schema vocabulary (RDFS) 2017-06-14', 'owl - The OWL 2 Schema vocabulary (OWL 2) 2017-06-14', 'rdf - The RDF Concepts Vocabulary (RDF) 2017-06-14', 'ssn - Semantic Sensor Network Ontology 2017-06-14', and 'qudt - Quantities, Units, Dimensions and Types (QUDT) Schema 2017-06-14'. The 'Latest Updates' section lists: 'qudt - Quantities, Units, Dimensions and Types (QUDT) Schema 2017-06-14', 'ssn - Semantic Sensor Network Ontology 2017-06-14', 'rdfs - The RDF Schema vocabulary (RDFS) 2017-06-14', 'rdf - The RDF Concepts Vocabulary (RDF) 2017-06-14', and 'owl - The OWL 2 Schema vocabulary (OWL 2) 2017-06-14'. The footer of the page contains the 'BIG DATA OCEAN' logo and the text 'BigDataOcean Repository'.

Figure 4: Visualisation of vocabularies in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository

Figure 5 shows the metadata about the Geonames ontology (gn). As can be seen, different properties of the ontology are registered in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository, e.g. URI, Namespace. Furthermore, statistics like number of classes or instances, provide an aggregated description of the ontology, while the expressivity denotes the type of properties that compose the ontology.

Figure 5: Presentation of vocabulary metadata

Figure 6 presents an interface where basic metadata about the ontology can be uploaded when an ontology is registered in the BigDataOcean metadata repository. Further properties like statistics and expressivity are computed once the registration of the ontology is completed.

Figure 6: Editing of vocabulary metadata

Figure 7 illustrates two of the data access methods provided by the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository. A SPARQL endpoint allows users to collect properties of the vocabularies by posing SPARQL queries on the SPARQL endpoint interface; answers of the queries will be listed at the bottom of the window. Furthermore, data dumps can be downloaded using different formats, e.g. n3 or nq.

Figure 7: SPARQL endpoint for querying vocabularies and their metadata

Figure 8 presents a visualisation of the connections between four vocabularies in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository. Connections are computed based on links between ontologies and associations between the datasets and pilots where these ontologies are utilised.

Figure 8: Visualisation of vocabularies in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository and their interconnections

The BigDataOcean Metadata Repository is available online as a Docker container⁶.

⁶ The source code of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository with installation instructions can be found here <http://github.com/EIS-Bonn/lov>. The project can be executed with the help of docker-compose following the instructions here <http://github.com/EIS-Bonn/BigDataOcean-LOV>.

6 BigDataOcean Vocabularies

In this chapter, the list of existing ontologies and vocabularies that will be used in the context of the BigDataOcean pilots and will be managed by the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository is documented. This list has been consolidated by studying the existing marine related ontologies and vocabularies in the literature and analysing the vocabulary requirements from the four pilots. Table 7 includes the initial list of BigDataOcean Linked Data vocabularies.

Table 7: List of Ontologies and Vocabularies in BigDataOcean

Name	Description	Link
Semantic Sensor Network Ontology	Describes sensors, actuators and observations, and related concepts. It does not describe domain concepts, time, locations, etc. these are intended to be included from other ontologies via OWL imports.	http://www.w3.org/ns/ssn/
Climate and Forecast (CF) Standard Names	(v.44) Ontology representation of the Climate and Forecast (CF) standard names parameter vocabulary, which is intended for use with climate and forecast data in the atmosphere, surface and ocean domains. Every CF parameter is captured as a SKOS concept.	http://mmisw.org/ont/cf/parameter
SeaDataNet sea areas	Sea area terms from the IHB (1953) list plus additional terms added under SeaDataNet governance. Additional SeaDataNet vocabs at http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/C16/current/
NASA SWEET ontology	Earth and Environmental Terminology	https://sweet.jpl.nasa.gov/sweet2.3
GEMET Thesaurus	Multilingual thesaurus that aims to define a core terminology for the environmental domain.	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet/rdf?langcode=en

QUDT catalog - Quantities, Units, Dimensions and Data Types Ontologies	The QUDT collection of ontologies define the base classes properties, and restrictions used for modelling physical quantities, units of measure, and their dimensions in various measurement systems.	http://www.qudt.org/release2/qudt-catalog.html
ICES Reference COde (RECO)	RECO is a database that manages all the codes, code types and lists that are used in International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) databases.	http://vocab.ices.dk/
GeoNames Ontology	The GeoNames Ontology makes it possible to add geospatial semantic information to the World Wide Web. All over 11 million geonames toponyms now have a unique URL with a corresponding RDF web service. Other services describe the relation between toponyms.	http://www.geonames.org/ontology/documentation.html
LinkedGeoData Ontology	LinkedGeoData ontology has been derived from concepts defined by Open Street Map	http://linkedgeodata.org/ontology
GeoSPARQL Ontology	GeoSPARQL ontology includes a long list of terms to represent spatial-objects in RDF. The GeoSPARQL ontology is used in the extension of SPARQL named GeoSPARQL to express SPARQL queries over spatial-objects.	http://schemas.opengis.net/geosparql/1.0/geosparql_vocab_all.rdf
CDIP Term Vocabulary	Coastal Data Information Program (CDIP) is an extensive network for monitoring waves and beaches along the coastlines of the United States. It has a vast database of publicly-accessible environmental data for use by coastal engineers and planners, scientists, mariners, and marine enthusiasts.	http://mmisw.org/ont/cdip/term

In addition, Table 8 includes general vocabularies for describing datasets and their quality.

Table 8: List of Ontologies and Vocabularies for datasets and dataset quality in BigDataOcean

Name	Description	Link
VANN	A vocabulary for annotating vocabulary descriptions	http://purl.org/vocab/vann/
VOAF (Vocabulary Of A Friend)	VOAF is a vocabulary specification providing elements allowing the description of vocabularies (RDFS vocabularies or OWL ontologies) used in the Linked Data Cloud. In particular it provides properties expressing the different ways such vocabularies can rely on, extend, specify, annotate or otherwise link to each other. It relies itself on Dublin Core and void.	http://purl.org/vocommons/voaf
Vocabulary of Interlinked Datasets (VoID)	The Vocabulary of Interlinked Datasets (VoID) is an RDF Schema vocabulary for expressing metadata about RDF datasets. It is intended as a bridge between the publishers and users of RDF data, with applications ranging from data discovery to cataloguing and archiving of datasets.	http://rdfs.org/ns/void#
Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT)	DCAT is an RDF vocabulary designed to facilitate interoperability between data catalogues published on the Web.	http://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat/

7 Conclusions

This document describes the requirements of the vocabularies and ontologies that will be used in the BigDataOcean platform in order to allow for the collection, harmonisation, and processing of multi-source big maritime data. For this purpose, a metadata repository is being developed that will provide the infrastructure for storing and managing these vocabularies and ontologies and their metadata. In the current deliverable, the requirements of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository are presented and based on these requirements an architectural design of the Metadata Repository is suggested. The first version of the BigDataOcean Repository is presented in this document with the use of corresponding screenshots. In addition, the related work in metadata repositories in the maritime domain is presented and compared to the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository. Finally, the initial list of vocabularies and ontologies that will be included in the repository is included. This list is based on the data source specification provided by the pilot partners during the requirements elicitation phase.

With this report the first phase of T3.1 (Big Data Semantic Vocabularies and Metadata Repository), i.e. M2-M6, has been concluded. During Month 15 and Month 19 (second phase of T3.1), new features of the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository will be delivered and new vocabularies will be contributed, based on the feedback by the project's end users. The collected vocabularies will provide a basis for D3.2, especially the harmonisation of data in BigDataOcean. In addition, outcomes of this deliverable will support tasks related to deliverable D2.2. Finally, the final version of the vocabularies and metadata repository will be provided in D3.3 - BigDataOcean Cross-Sector Semantics, Analytics and Business Intelligence Algorithms in M19.